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BODY AWARENESS AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH PAIN SEVERITY IN INDIVIDUALS WITH CHRONIC NECK PAIN: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

KRONİK BOYUN AĞRISI OLAN BİREYLERDE BEDEN FARKINDALIĞI VE AĞRI ŞİDDETİ İLE İLİŞKİSİ: SİSTEMATİK DERLEME

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Abstract

Recent scientific studies emphasize the importance of body perception and body awareness. Body awareness has been reported to be impaired in several chronic pain conditions. The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between body awareness and pain intensity in patients with non-specific chronic neck pain. The PubMed, Cochrane Library and Pedro databases were searched for studies up to July 2024. Each database was searched independently using a specific replication search sequence. Two studies (one cross-sectional study, one randomized clinical trial) were included in this review. Based on the results of these studies, body awareness appears to be significantly associated with pain intensity in patients with chronic neck pain. Therefore, incorporating body awareness training into treatment plans is recommended as a potential mechanism for reducing pain intensity in chronic neck pain.

Keywords: Neck Pain, Chronic Pain, Body Awareness

Özet

Son bilimsel çalışmalar beden algısı ve beden farkındalığının önemini vurgulamaktadır. Beden farkındalığının çeşitli kronik ağrı durumlarında bozulduğu bildirilmiştir. Bu çalışmanın amacı, spesifik olmayan kronik boyun ağrısı olan hastalarda beden farkındalığı ile ağrı yoğunluğu arasındaki ilişkiyi araştırmaktır. PubMed, Cochrane Kütüphanesi ve Pedro veri tabanları Temmuz 2024'e kadar olan çalışmalar için arandı. Her veritabanı belirli bir tekrar arama dizisi kullanılarak bağımsız olarak arandı. Bu incelemeye iki çalışma (bir kesitsel çalışma, bir randomize klinik çalışma) dahil edildi. Bu çalışmaların sonuçlarına göre, beden farkındalığının kronik boyun ağrısı olan hastalarda ağrı yoğunluğu ile önemli ölçüde ilişkili olduğu görülmektedir. Bu nedenle, beden farkındalığı eğitiminin

tedavi planlarına dahil edilmesi, kronik boyun ağrısında ağrı yoğunluğunu azaltmak için olası bir mekanizma olarak önerilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Boyun Ağrısı, Kronik Ağrı, Beden Farkındalığı

INTRODUCTION

Neck pain is one of the most common musculoskeletal problems and is an important cause of disability from a public health perspective, as well as causing serious socio-economic difficulties (Blanpied et al., 2017). Neck pain lasting three months or longer is defined as chronic neck pain (CNP) (Jensen & Harms-Ringdahl, 2007) and is becoming increasingly common in society (Takasawa et al., 2015). CNP can greatly affect the quality of life of individuals; it can cause depression, anxiety and loss of productivity (Coulter et al., 2019; Dance et al., 2016). In addition, it has been shown that body awareness of individuals with chronic pain is impaired, and this may make pain management difficult (Smith et al., 2008). Neck pain can be associated with serious conditions such as neurological conditions, infections, neoplasms and cervical spine fractures, or it can be idiopathic (neck pain with no known cause) (Australian Acute Musculoskeletal Pain Guidelines Group, 2004). Neck pain that occurs without a specific systemic disease or pain-causing pathology is defined as Non-Specific Neck Pain (Kaka et al., 2016; Tsakitidis et al., 2013).

Body awareness is referred to as intrinsic awareness or intrinsic sensitivity (Mehling et al., 2012; Pollatos et al., 2012). This concept is defined as an individual's ability to be sensitive to and recognise subtle bodily changes in response to internal and external conditions (Andersen, 2006; Price & Thompson, 2007; Spoor et al., 2005). From a neuroscientific point of view, awareness of one's own body is a very important and specialized form of cognition and a fundamental factor for the life of the organism. This awareness allows us to observe our homeostatic status, to predict body damage and to protect

ourselves from dangers. It is also extremely important in the creation and control of movement (JL B., 2009). Research has shown that individuals with chronic pain experience perceptual problems such as swelling or numbness and impaired sense of position (Hidalgo et al., 2013; Maihöfner et al., 2006; Moseley & Flor, 2012).

Findings in the literature suggest that body awareness may be impaired in individuals with chronic neck pain and this impairment may contribute to the persistence of pain (Cramer et al., 2013; Lauche et al., 2012). Therefore, the aim of this systematic review is to examine the relationship between chronic neck pain and body awareness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Moher et al., 2009).

Research question

The search question for this systematic review was: "What is the evidence for the relationship between body awareness and pain severity in individuals with chronic neck pain?" A systematic review of the scientific literature was conducted to identify studies reporting body awareness and pain assessment in patients with non-specific chronic neck pain (NSCNP).

Data sources and search strategy

The three electronic databases MEDLINE/PubMed, Cochrane Library web search and Physiotherapy Evidence Database (PEDro) were searched for English-language observational and experimental studies published between 1990 and July 2024. The search strategy consisted of a mixture of free-text terms and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH). Details of the search strategy can be found in Supplementary Table 1.

perception[Title/Abstract] OR Self-perception[Title/Abstract] OR Body image[Title/Abstract] OR Interoceptive awareness[Title/Abstract] OR Mindfulness[Title/Abstract] OR Bodily awareness[Title/Abstract] OR Body oriented[Title/Abstract] OR Neck awareness[Title/Abstract] OR body therapy[Title/Abstract] OR body mind therapy[Title/Abstract] OR movement therapy[Title/Abstract] OR body awareness therapy[Title/Abstract])		
#1 AND #2	534 results	#1 AND #2
Key Words	Cochrane	Key Words
#1 MeSH descriptor: [Neck Pain] explode all trees #2 MeSH descriptor: [Chronic Pain] explode all trees #3 MeSH descriptor: [Pain] explode all trees #4 neck NEXT (pain OR disability OR ache OR aches):ti,ab,kw #5 (Bournemouth Neck Questionnaire OR Cervical Spine Outcomes Questionnaire OR Copenhagen Neck Functional Disability Scale OR Neck Pain and Disability Scale OR Northwick Park Neck Pain Questionnaire OR Neck disability index):ti,ab,kw #6 (Ache OR Aches OR Cervicalgia OR neckache):ti,ab,kw #7 (pain NEXT (chronic OR chronic neck OR acute OR acute neck OR non-specific OR nonspecific)):ti,ab,kw #8 #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7		
#9 MeSH descriptor: [Body Image] explode all trees #10 MeSH descriptor: [Mindfulness] explode all trees #11 (body NEXT (awareness OR perception OR oriented OR therapy OR mind therapy OR awareness therapy)):ti,ab,kw #12 (self NEXT (perception OR focus OR awareness)):ti,ab,kw #13 (awareness NEXT (neck OR bodily OR Interoceptive)):ti,ab,kw #14 ("movement therapy"):ti,ab,kw #15 #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13 OR #14		
#8 AND #15	433 results	#8 AND #15

Key Words	PubMed	Key Words
#1 neck pain[Title/Abstract] OR cervical pain[Title/Abstract] OR neck ache[Title/Abstract] OR neck disability[Title/Abstract] OR Bournemouth Neck Questionnaire[Title/Abstract] OR Cervical Spine Outcomes Questionnaire[Title/Abstract] OR Copenhagen Neck Functional Disability Scale[Title/Abstract] OR Neck Pain[Title/Abstract] AND Disability Scale[Title/Abstract] OR Northwick Park Neck Pain Questionnaire[Title/Abstract] OR Neck disability index[Title/Abstract] OR acute neck pain[Title/Abstract] OR chronic neck pain[Title/Abstract] OR Chronic pain[Title/Abstract] OR Pain[Title/Abstract] OR Ache[Title/Abstract] OR Aches[Title/Abstract] OR Non-specific pain[Title/Abstract] OR Nonspecific pain[Title/Abstract] OR Cervicalgia[Title/Abstract] OR neckache[Title/Abstract])	85,942 results	
#2 (Body awareness[Title/Abstract] OR Self-awareness[Title/Abstract] OR Self-focus[Title/Abstract] OR Body	4,344 results	

Data extraction

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Articles on body awareness in people with neck pain.
- Articles that include individuals with chronic NSCNP of any age group.
- Articles with body awareness as the primary outcome measure.
- Articles with measures of neck pain (e.g. severity, frequency, duration and/or disability) assessed using validated instruments as secondary outcomes.
- Experimental and observational articles evaluating the relationship between body awareness and NSCNP.
- Articles written in English.

Exclusion criteria

- Reviews, meta-analyses, editorials, case reports/case series, conference proceedings, editorials, letters and poster presentations

- Articles that include neck pain associated with radiculopathy in addition to a specific underlying pathology such as fracture, rheumatoid arthritis, osteoporosis, or whiplash.
- Articles that include other complaints associated with neck pain (headache, migraine, etc.)
- Articles in languages other than English

Study selection

All titles and abstracts were imported into Excel and duplicates and irrelevant articles that did not meet the inclusion criteria were removed. Two reviewers independently screened the titles, abstracts and study references of the articles for eligibility criteria. The same reviewers then reviewed the full texts of all relevant articles. In case of disagreement, a third and fourth reviewer were consulted for a final decision.

Quality assessment

Methodological quality (risk of bias) was assessed using the JBI appraisal checklist for cross-sectional studies and the PEDro scale for randomized controlled trials (RCTs). Two reviewers independently assessed the quality of each study. Disagreements were resolved by consensus. The JBI appraisal checklist for analytical cross-sectional studies consists of 8 items, each of which is scored as (yes=1), (no=0) or (unclear/not applicable=0). The PEDro scale ranks RCTs based on classifications of methodological quality as follows 'poor' (score 0-4), 'fair' (4-5), 'good' (6-8) and 'excellent' (9-10) (de Morton, 2009; Maher et al., 2003).

RESULTS

Study selection

Three different database searches identified 972 trials. Duplicate studies (n=456) and studies that did not meet the preliminary eligibility criteria (n=516) were excluded. The full text of 15 articles was examined by two reviewers and two articles were finally included in this systematic review. A summary of the study selection flowchart is shown in Figure 1

Fig 1. PRISMA_2020_flor_diagram_new_SRs_v1.

*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

Source: Page MJ, et al. BMJ 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

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Study characteristics

The results suggest that there may be a reciprocal effect between neck pain and neck perception. Because of this effect, incorporating pain management and postural correction strategies into rehabilitation programmes may increase the effectiveness of the treatment process. Therefore, it may be appropriate to include neck awareness approaches in rehabilitation programmes.

There are different definitions of body awareness in the literature, and because of these different definitions, it is a complex concept. It involves the conscious perception of sensations arising from interoceptive or exteroceptive sensory channels related to the body and is shaped by a multidimensional process influenced by motor commands as well as beliefs and attitudes about the body (Bekker et al., 2008; Haugstad et al., 2006). Therefore, evaluating body awareness is challenging, and there is no gold standard of measurement method. Body awareness disorders can be assessed in different ways, such as self-report questionnaires, drawings, or animations of perceived distortions. For example, in the study by Erkan included in this review, body awareness was assessed using the Fremantle Neck Awareness Questionnaire, while in the study by Lauche et al. (2016), the Postural Awareness Scale was used. In both studies, pain severity was assessed with the VAS (Visual Analog Scale), which has long been considered the gold standard for pain severity assessment (Erkan et al., 2023; Lauche et al., 2016).

Significant correlations between pain severity and body awareness have been reported in various chronic pain conditions. In the low back pain population, there is substantial evidence supporting a direct relationship between body awareness disturbances and pain severity (Levenig et al., 2019;

Meier et al., 2019; Wand et al., 2017). The findings of this review align with the literature, showing that the results obtained from individuals with chronic neck pain are consistent with those from other pain populations. Although the underlying mechanisms of this relationship are not yet fully understood, changes in body awareness may play a role in the experience of chronic neck pain, suggesting that this area should be considered in this population.

This review provides new approaches for understanding and managing the interaction between body awareness disorders and pain in patients with neck pain. In the 2017 study by Lauche et al., it was reported that the more chronic neck pain patients were aware of their posture, the less effort they expended in maintaining this awareness, and the more they recognized the connection between posture and well-being, the more their pain decreased (Lauche et al., 2016). This finding suggests that the connection between posture awareness and pain may play a fundamental role in the process of changing habitual postures and movement patterns.

Although there is significant evidence of the presence of postural disorders in neck pain in recent years, there is insufficient evidence regarding the relationship between pain severity and postural disorder (Erkan et al., 2023; Lauche et al., 2016). This review, conducted with two studies, highlights the need for more evidence in future research to better understand the relationship between pain severity and body awareness in neck pain.

Based on the findings of this systematic review, body awareness appears to be significantly related to pain intensity in patients with chronic neck pain. Therefore, incorporating body awareness training into treatment plans is recommended as a potential mechanism for reducing pain intensity in NSCNP. Including this aspect in clinical research could further enhance the understanding and effectiveness of interventions. These insights may assist in designing personalized exercise interventions tailored to the needs of patients with chronic neck pain.

Quality assessment

Table 3 and 4 presents the results of the quality assessment score of each study. Both two studies had high methodological quality.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results suggest that there may be a reciprocal effect between neck pain and neck perception. Because of this effect, incorporating pain management and postural correction strategies into rehabilitation programmes may increase the effectiveness of the treatment process. Therefore, it may be appropriate to include neck awareness approaches in rehabilitation programmes.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Table 2. Characteristics of studies

References	Aim	Design	Participants	Gender	Age (years)	Pain Duration (months)	Pain Severity (VAS)	Outcome Measures	Results
Erkan et al., 2023	To compare neck awareness, muscular endurance, mental state, and self-efficacy in young adults with and without neck pain, and to examine the relationship of awareness with pain intensity, muscular endurance, and anxiety/depression in the neck pain group.	Cross-sectional	Chronic neck pain (n=41): At least 3 months and scored above 0 on the VAS. Healthy group (n=63): No neck pain in the last 6 months.	30 female	23.17 ± 3.87	20.53 ± 11.64	4.86	Pain Severity: Visual Analog Scale (VAS) Body Awareness: Fremantle Neck Awareness Questionnaire	p=0.310. In the neck pain group, a positive correlation was found between FreBAQ value and pain severity, muscular endurance, and mental state.
Lauch et al., 2016	To investigate the efficacy of Tai Chi compared with neck exercises and no treatment in improving neck pain, disability, and quality of life in subjects with chronic nonspecific neck pain.	Three-arm randomized controlled trial	Chronic non-specific neck pain (n=114): At least 45 mm or higher on VAS.	91 female	49.4 ± 11.7	Not specified	50.7 ± 20.4	Pain Severity: Visual Analog Scale (VAS) Body Awareness: Postural Awareness Scale	Regression analysis revealed that reductions in pain intensity from baseline to 12 weeks were associated with an increase in the Effortless Awareness and Connectedness score from the Postural Awareness Scale (r ² =0.078, p=0.0033).

Table 3. Methodologic quality of cross-sectional study

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Summary score	Total percentage	Quality
Raziye Erkan, et al., 2023	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	6	%75	High Quality

*Yes=1, No=0, Not applicable: Unclear or not applicable=0

Table 4. Methodologic quality of Randomized controlled trial study

	e	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Total score	Quality
Romy Lauche et al., 2016	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	9	Excellent